

On the Variability of Valency.

BY SIB PRAFULLA CHANDRA RÂY, Kt., C.I.E., D.Sc., Ph.D.,

President, Indian Chemical Society.

The conception of valency has undergone many changes since it was first formulated by Berzelius. The idea of constant valency derived from the behaviour of carbon compounds and so strongly upheld by Kekulé and others had to ultimately give way to that of variable valency, as serious difficulties were encountered in representing the formulæ of inorganic compounds. Valency may now be regarded as a variable function of several factors. These latter may be summed up as follows :

(1) The valency of an atom varies according to the nature of the combining atoms. The nitrogen behaves as mono-, di-, tri-, tetra-, and penta-valent towards oxygen but only trivalent towards chlorine. Sulphur is hexavalent towards oxygen and fluorine as in SO_2 and SF_6 ; but its maximum valency towards chlorine is only four as given by SCl_4 . Manganese is heptavalent in its highest oxide Mn_2O_7 , but becomes tetravalent in its highest chloride. Iron is di- and tri-valent towards chlorine but is hexavalent towards oxygen.

(2) The valency of an element also depends upon external conditions.

(a) Thus valency often varies with temperature,—generally decreasing with increasing temperature. Dissociation of PCl_5 , CO_2 , SO_2 , I_2 , S_8 etc. furnishes instances of the kind.

(b) Pressure also exerts a similar influence retarding the dissociation of many compounds with a higher valency of the central atom into those of a lower valency.

(c) Medium also plays an important rôle in certain cases. Thus some compounds can exist only in solution or in the solid state. For example compounds like HI_3 , HBr_3 , HClI_2 , HClBr_2 , and HBrI_2 , are known in solution only; and KICl_4 , NH_4ICl_4 , KIBr_4 , and NH_4IBr_4 , are known only in the solid state.

(d) Presence or absence of certain substances in the medium can also determine the condition of valency. Thus the tetravalent oxygen of H_2O_2 becomes unstable in aqueous solution containing hydroxyl ions, whereas hydrogen ions increase its stability. Attention might also be drawn in this connection to the influence of minute traces of water vapour in bringing about or retarding

many commonplace reactions as has been so ably demonstrated by Prof. Baker.

(e) Relative concentration of the reacting atoms also affects the combining capacity of the central atoms. Chlorine in excess acting upon phosphorus forms PCl_5 , whereas phosphorus in excess acting upon chlorine generates PCl_3 .

A consideration of all these facts led to the doctrine of variable valency which formulates that it is not an inherent property of the atom as such but depends upon the nature of the atoms with which it combines and also upon external physical conditions.

Further changes in this fundamental conception of valency were introduced later on to explain many new important properties of substances as they were gradually discovered. One of the most striking contributions in this direction was made by Alfred Werner—the father of co-ordination chemistry. The theory was advanced by him to elucidate the constitution of the so-called molecular or complex compounds which presented serious difficulties to the application of the existing theories of valency. After many unsuccessful efforts made by Blomstrand, Jörgensen and others, it was left to Werner to bring law and order into this chaotic region of complex compounds. The success which this theory has attained is too well-known to be elaborated here. One of the fundamental assumptions of the co-ordination theory is that the central combining atom possesses a maximum co-ordination value of 4, 6 or 8 according as it is di-, tri- or tetra-valent. The atom always tends to satisfy the maximum co-ordination value. But as in the case of simple or primary valencies, maximum co-ordination or complex valency also changes according to the nature of the co-ordinated atoms, groups or radicles and is further influenced by external physical conditions. A host of compounds can be named in which the co-ordination number is one, two, three, five, seven, eight and even more than that, though these compounds are not so stable as the cobalt and platinum compounds with sixfold co-ordination. Some typical examples of these are given here.

Co-ordination value one: $\text{AgX}\cdot\text{NH}_3$; $\text{AuCl}\cdot\text{NH}_3$.

Twofold co-ordination: $\text{AgX}\cdot 2\text{NH}_3$; $\text{CuCl}\cdot\text{Me}_2\text{S}$; $\text{CuCl}\cdot\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$;
 $\text{AuCl}\cdot\text{Me}_2\text{S}$.
 $\text{AgNO}_3\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{CN})_2$; $\text{CuBr}\cdot\text{P}(\text{OCH}_3)_3$;
 $\text{AgCN}\cdot\text{KCN}$; $\text{AgSCN}\cdot\text{KSCN}$; $\text{AuCl}\cdot\text{KCl}$;
 $\text{KF}\cdot\text{HF}$; $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{ICl}$; $\text{CuCN}\cdot\text{KCN}$.

Threefold co-ordination: $\text{CuX} \cdot 3\text{NH}_3$; $\text{CuCl} \cdot 3\text{Py}$; $\text{AuCl} \cdot 3\text{NH}_3$;
 $[\text{Cu} \cdot [\text{CS}(\text{NH}_2)_2]_3] \text{X}$; $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{Py}$;
 $\text{HgCl}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}$.
 $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{CO}$; $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{PCl}_3$; $2\text{KCN} \cdot \text{NiCN}$;
 $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot \text{KCl}$; $\text{HgI}_2 \cdot \text{KI}$; $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SX}$;
 $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{C} \cdot \text{Cl}$.

II

Fivefold co-ordination: $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_5] \text{SO}_4$; $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{NH}_3$;
 $\text{CdCl}_2 \cdot 5\text{NH}_3$; $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{O}$.

Sevenfold co-ordination: $\text{LiI} \cdot 7\text{NH}_3$; $\text{SiF}_4 \cdot 3\text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{F}$;
 $\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot 2\text{HCl}$; $\text{BiI}_3 \cdot 4\text{KI}$.

Eightfold co-ordination: $\text{Mo}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 4\text{MeCN}$; $\text{W}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 4\text{MeCN}$;
 $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_8] \text{Pt}(\text{CNS})_6$.

From what has been said above it can now be concluded that valency is not an invariable characteristic of an element as its atomic weight is; nay, even the latter, after the discovery of isotopes by Aston has ceased to be a constant. Hence both the normal and co-ordination valencies of an atom may change with changing circumstances. An elementary atom which usually exhibits di- and tetra-valency may under special conditions become tri-, penta-, and hexa-valent as well. I shall deal here with two special cases only, that of platinum and gold.

The platinum atom, as is well known, generally gives compounds of the types PtX_2 and PtX_4 in which platinum is di- and tetra-valent respectively. Compounds of different types have also been described in the literature. The following oxides and chlorides of the metal have been described: PtO , Pt_2O_3 , PtO_2 , PtO_3 , PtCl , PtCl_2 , PtCl_3 , and PtCl_4 . These clearly indicate that the platinum atom can manifest mono-, di-, tri-, tetra- and hexa-valency.

Gold is also usually regarded as mono- and tri-valent but it also acts as divalent as in the compounds AuO (gold dioxide) and AuSO_4 (auroso-auric sulphate).

It has already been shown with respect to mercaptanic radicles and organic sulphides that platinum exhibits all different valencies up to a maximum of eight.

With dithio-ethylene glycol $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SH})_2$, platinum chloride reacts according to the following scheme giving compounds of ter-, quadri-

quinque-, sexa- and octa-valent platinum according to the conditions of the experiment.

The nature of the compounds obtained greatly depends upon the temperature of the reaction. With increasing temperature compounds of decreasing valency of platinum are obtained. This is in line with the general observation already made that rise of temperature tends to lower the valence of an elementary atom. Further it should also be noticed that in no case the valency of platinum has been found to exceed eight as is required by its position in the periodic table.

Now turning to the complex compounds of platinum obtained by the action of chloroplatinic acid upon ethyl sulphide under different experimental conditions, a similar observation regarding the co-ordination valency of platinum can be made. The compounds obtained may be tabulated as below:

- (a) $\text{PtCl}_4\cdot\text{Et}_2\text{S}$.
- (b) $\text{PtCl}_4\cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$.
- (c) $\text{PtCl}_3\cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$.
- (d) $\text{PtCl}_2\cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$.
- (e) $\text{PtCl}_2\cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Some of these compounds under (b) and (d) have already been described by Blomstrand, Tschugaeff and Malschewsky. The compound (b) has been isolated in six different isomeric modifications. Of these two have already been described by Blomstrand and are known as *cis-trans* isomers.

Compound (a) may be regarded to exhibit a co-ordination value of two only. Of the six isomers of the compound (b) in which the co-ordination value is evidently four, constitution of the three can be accounted for in the following way:

- (1) Blomstrand's *cis*-compound.
- (2) Blomstrand's *trans*-compound.
- (3) $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_4]\text{PtCl}_4$.

Compound (c) can be represented as molecular compound of (b) and (d). $[(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{PtCl}_2]_2$ $[(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2\text{PtCl}_2]$ or $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_4]$ PtCl_4 .

The former is preferred as, on crystallization from alcohol, it breaks up into the two constituent molecules. This is further confirmed by the action of ammonia upon it, which

gives an ammonical complex $\left[\overset{\text{II}}{\text{Pt}} (\text{NH}_3)_6 \right] \text{Cl}_2$.

Compound (e) can be constituted as $\text{H}_2 \left[\text{Pt} \begin{array}{c} \text{Cl}_2 \\ \text{OH} \end{array} \right] (\text{Et}_2\text{S})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ showing a higher co-ordination value than six.

Compound (a) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ cannot be adequately represented by Werner's theory and it must be assumed that the co-ordination value of the monovalent platinum atom is two. By the action of bases like ethylamine, benzylamine, pyridine and piperidine it gives compounds of the type, $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{B}$; $\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot \text{B}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}$; $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{B}$; $2\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{B} \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}$.

The compound (e) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, by the action of bases, gives compounds of the type $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{B}$ and $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{B}$.

Similar compounds have also been obtained from platinum chloride and benzyl sulphide.

What has been stated regarding the valency of platinum applies equally well to the case of gold. As is well-known gold usually forms compounds of the mono- and tri-valent type and only in rare cases of the divalent type. But with respect to mercaptanic radicles it resembles platinum forming compounds in which it behaves as a bi-, ter-, quadri-, and quinque-valent atom. Diethyl disulphide and auric chloride have been found to give a crystalline compound of the composition $2\text{AuCl}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}_2$, the gold apparently behaving as divalent and a white amorphous powder having the composition $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}_2$.

By the action of auric chloride upon the monopotassium salt of dithio-ethylene glycol, a compound of the composition $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}_4(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_2$, has been obtained. This can be represented constitutionally either as

In the first case one atom of gold acting in bi- and the other atom in ter-valent condition. In the second case it is regarded as a molecular compound of aurous chloride with quadrivalent auric thioglycollate.

Benzaldiene tetrasulphide with auric chloride yields the compound,

which may be represented as a molecular compound like

the gold functioning as mono- and bi-valent. When, however, benzaldiene trisulphide is similarly treated, the molecule is broken up and compounds of diethylene disulphide are obtained, thus:

1:4-Dithian.

The following compounds have thus been obtained:—

(a) 6A.Au₂Cl₃

(b) 5A.Au₂Cl₃

(c) 4A.Au₂Cl₃

(d) 4A.Au₂Cl₃

(e) 3A.Au₂Cl₃

(f) 3A.Au₂Cl₃

where A=1:4-dithian.

It is very difficult to explain the anomalous nature of these chlorides according to our usual conception of the valency of gold.

Compound (a) can only be represented as a sulphonium compound in which the gold behaves as bi- and ter-valent respectively.

Compound (b) and (c) can be regarded as molecular compounds like 5A, 2AuCl, AuCl₃; 4A, 2AuCl, AuCl₃. Compounds (d) and (e) should be regarded as sulphonium compounds like (a), and (f) as a molecular compound of 2AuCl.3A.

Triethylene trisulphide with auric chloride on the other hand gives two compounds, namely, 2AuCl₃.(C₂H₄S)₃ and (C₂H₄S)₃.AuCl₃. These can of course be represented as simple molecular compounds of trivalent and bivalent gold respectively. Or, we may consider them as sulphonium compounds with quinquevalent and quadrivalent gold respectively.

By the interaction of sodium dithioethylene glycol and auric

chloride in acetone solution a quinquevalent gold compound of the formula,

has been obtained. When the reaction occurs in ethereal solution, the compound $\text{Au}_5\text{Cl}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{S}_2)_4$ is obtained, the gold retaining its tervalency intact.

The action of bases like ammonia and pyridine upon some of these gold compounds has been studied. In almost all the cases the final products consist of molecular compounds of monovalent gold, AuCl .

By the action of ammonia upon $\text{Au}_5\text{Cl}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$, a compound of the composition $\text{Au}_5\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 6\text{NH}_3$ has been obtained which cannot be accounted for by the usually accepted valencies of gold.

It can thus be concluded that valency is variable, and it is significant that two of the most noble metals platinum and gold exhibit the greatest possible variation in this respect.¹

References :

1. Werner, *Neuere Anschauungen auf dem Gebiete der Anorganischen Chemie*.
2. Weinland, *Einführung in die Chemie der Komplexverbindungen*.
3. Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 133.
4. Blomstrand, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1888, (ii), 38, 352.
5. Tschugaeff and Malschewsky, *Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 138, 385.
6. Tschugaeff, *Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1913, 82, 420.
7. Rây and Bose-Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 178.
8. Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 63.
9. Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 155.
10. Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 872; 1922, 121, 1, 83.

Presidential Address delivered at the Third Annual General Meeting of the Indian Chemical Society held at Lahore on the 5th January, 1927.